

Devotion in Colours and Gold: The Art of Tanjore Paintings

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Abstract

Tanjore Painting, also known by the name Thanjavur Painting, is an ancient South Indian art form that was named after the city from where it originated. Locally, Tanjore Paintings are also called 'Palagai Padam' means picture on a wooden plank as these paintings are crafted on wooden planks. The innovative painting style, vibrant colours, iconic composition and surface richness make Tanjore Paintings unique and popular across the world. Each Tanjore Painting is embellished with glass beads, semi-precious gems and stones, vibrant natural colours and glittering gold foil. All these provide a three-dimensional effect to the painting. The art form got its original inspiration from 1600 A.D., when the Nayaks were under the control of Rayas of Vijayanagar. During this period, Rayas encouraged various forms of classical art, including dance, painting, music and literature. However, the painting style as we know it today is highly influenced by the Maratha court of Tanjore. In 2007-2008, the Government of India recognized Tanjore Painting as a Geographical Indication. The skilled artisans use this painting style to paint the portraits of Hindu Gods and Goddesses in different postures.

Keywords: *Tanjore Painting, Palagai Padam, vibrant colours, gold foil, Nayaks, Vijayanagar, Maratha court of Tanjore*

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Introduction

Paintings as an art form has flourished in India from very early periods as is evident from literary sources and also from the remnants that have been discovered. Numerous paintings or isolated paintings, framed drawings and long scroll of paintings, representing a complete legend. Thanjavur Painting is a classical South Indian painting style originated from the town of Thanjavur in Tamil Nadu. Thanjavur city has contributed a lot to the history of Indian art. The city has been the heart of art and architecture for centuries. Thanjavur was the capital of the Chola dynasty from 9th to 13th century, and during this period, Thanjavur reached new heights in art and architecture. The Brihadeesvara Temple is the symbol of this period and houses several wall paintings from the Chola Empire and Nayaka period. Thanjavur paintings are characterized by rich and vivid colours, simple iconic composition, glittering gold foils overlaid on delicate but extensive gesso work and inlay of glass beads and pieces or very rarely precious and semi-precious gems. In Thanjavur paintings we can see the influence of Deccan, Vijayanagar, Marathas and even European or Company styles of Painting.

Art Through the Ages

In the paintings of Pre - historic (Mesolithic) period, musical instruments like the harp figure to show that the awareness of creation of sound and the concept of rhythm had appeared.

Thousands of years later, paintings appear on the seals of the Harappa Civilization. The Indus valley people were very fond of painting. Different kinds of figures and designs were drawn on earthen wares and utensils. The Indus valley people had achieved a great skill in drawing the figures of men, animals and various other objects of nature.

In the paintings of the later period, men are depicted as riding on cattle and elephants, battle scenes, royal processions, men riding garrisoned horses, etc. The Pallavas also left behind excellent examples of paintings in temples. The Cholas promoted both paintings and sculptures.

The turbulent conditions that existed in Northern India during the Middle Ages resulted in an exodus of artists and poets to the South, and the Vijayanagar kingdom fostered a great burgeoning of the arts, particularly of paintings. The Vijayanagar artist was responsible for the development of three distinct schools of art –Deccan School, Mysore school and Thanjavur School. The Mysore school reached its zenith during the rule of Mummadi Krishnaraja Wodeyar on 18th century, while in Thanjavur, the Maratha kings developed a distinct style of painting. The credit for the development and establishment of this ornate style of ‘Tanjore Paintings,’ as they are known, goes to Serfoji Maharaja of Thanjavur.

History of Tanjore Paintings

The roots of Tanjore Paintings are also linked to Thanjavur. The painting style originated and flourished in 16th and 17th centuries. The origin of this classical painting style is linked to the Vijayanagar Empire (1336 A.D. to 1646 A.D.), including the areas of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh. The rulers of Vijayanagar were patrons of art and culture. The roots of this South Indian art form are linked to the Mural Art of the Vijayanagar Empire.

Tanjore Painting was first used for decorating the doors and walls of homes, palaces and temples in Thanjavur. The interior walls of the palaces were also painted with depictions of various events like a coronation, battle victories and other achievements of the rulers. In contrast, the walls of temples and homes were decorated with murals and paintings involving religious themes and portraits of various

Hindu deities.

The remains of these ancient wall paintings are still present on the walls of Virupaksha Temple in Hampi, the capital city of Vijayanagar Empire, Varadaraja Temple, Kamakshi Temple in Kanchipuram, and Lepakshi Temple in Andhra Pradesh. Some of these paintings are also present in the Brihadeeswara Temple’s Gopuram of Periyar Kovil in Thanjavur.

During the reign of Vijayanagar, the Rayas of Vijayanagar administered the kingdom through Nayak Governors. These Governors also administered the outlying states under the supervision of the Raya of Vijayanagar. During the reign of Achyutappa (1564-1614), the Vijayanagar Empire fell, and several philosophers, artists, musicians, and litterateurs migrated to Thanjavur, Madurai and Mysore. Raghunatha Nayak, the son and successor of Achyutappa, was the most successful Nayak ruler and patron of art and artists. He established a unique school for Thanjavur artists, who later evolved the Tanjore Painting style during the reign of Marathas. The Maratha rulers were great patrons of art and artists. During the reign of Serfoji II in Thanjavur, the Tanjore Painting style flourished into its current form.

Development of Tanjore Paintings During Marathas And British

The royal Maratha artisans induced innovation into the traditional Tanjore Painting style to make it more royal and astonishing. They introduced ornamentation of Tanjore Paintings by using gesso work, glass beads, precious and semi-precious gems and gold foil to bring out the glow. Maratha artisans also introduced the reverse class painting technique into the Tanjore Painting style. Serfoji II’s reign was when Tanjore Painting and other art forms underwent innovation and greatly flourished.

After the Maratha rule ended with the death of the last Maratha ruler – Shivaji II, the Britishers annexed the state of Thanjavur. The mercantile Chettiars patronized the art form in Thanjavur and around South India. Being Shaivites, the Chettiar community encouraged Tanjore Painting with Shaivite themes. The monastery in Koviloor, Tamil Nadu, has a huge Tanjore Painting depicting the

lives of all 63 Shaivite Saints or Nayanmars and 64 miracles of Lord Shiva (Thiruvilaiyadal Puranam). Thanjavur's Bhimarajagoswami monastery has a large Tanjore Painting of 108 temples of Lord Vishnu. Britishers who came to the city of Thanjavur also patronized the South Indian art forms and encouraged Tanjore Painting style.

Even after the end of the Maratha Empire and the overpowering of the East India Company, the South Indian art form received huge popularity. After the wake of the Mysore wars in 1767-1799, the East India Company settled in the state of Thanjavur and greatly patronized the Tanjore Painting style.

Later in 1773, when the East India Company installed its military base in the city for British troops, the skilled Tanjore artisans illustrated their art for British personnel. The painting style appealed to British taste and sensibility. The Britishers inclined toward the South Indian art form and encouraged Indian artisans to portray different scenes of Indian festivals, rituals, flora and fauna in Tanjore paintings.

Primary Colours

The paintings are characterized by the use of primary colours, generally avoiding mixtures, with stylized modelling effects by shading the inside of the contours. Jewels, drapery and architectural elements like pillars and canopies are slightly raised as in low relief by the use of a special plaster covered with pure gold-leaf and embedded with semi-precious stones in different hues. Sometimes gold-coated silver-leaf was used. Colourful glass pieces and occasionally pearls were used to embellish the Thanjavur painting, which feature gave it an edge over the Mysore painting. The painter himself produced the colours, which were prepared along the lines described in ancient texts. Besides minerals, he used the leaves and flowers of certain plants. In modern times, waterproof plywood, which has the advantage of being available in any size is used. Thick brown paper or thin cardboard is pasted, utilizing maida (flour) or tamarind seed paste as an adhesive. The paper is fixed on the wooden plank with the help of a rich paste of the required thickness. Over this paste, unbleached long cloth or mull is spread smoothly, avoiding wrinkles. This

surface is then coated with a combination of gem Arabic, French chalk powder, copper sulphate and a little gopi (yellow powder). Thus treated, the surface is later played with a rounded glass, usually a paper – weight or a bottle. To obtain the best results, the surface has to be absolutely smooth. Formerly, sketching charcoal was obtained from straight twigs of the tamarind tree, which were cut to a suitable size and placed on a heated iron table. The charred twigs were then used as sketching charcoal.

Colours of mineral origin were reduced to powder in a mortar and, after being soaked in water for several hours, were made into a fine paste before being applied. When primary colours were mixed, they were ground in the mortar for proper blending, to obtain the distinct colours needed. Brushes for painting were generally made of squirrel's hair. These were needed for delicate work. For drawing superfine lines, brushes made of the pointed blade of a special variety of grass had to be used. Today, these conventional stipulations are, however, dispensed with, if easier and equally effective alternatives are available.

Features of Tanjore Paintings

A rough sketch of the picture is drawn with a crayon. For pictures of larger proportions, if a copy of the standard picture is available, a perforated stencil is used to draw the outline. The next step is to draw the sketch and then paint the farthest objects such as the sky or river. The animal and human figures, their dress and ornaments, need greater attention, and here the taste and the choice of the painter generally reveal his artistic inclinations. It is the degree of embellishment that is the distinguishing feature of a Thanjavur painting. Hence the importance of the gesso work or gold-covering of portions of jewellery. The gold work is generally taken up in the morning. When the picture and base of the gold-foil is moist, so as to hold the foil firmly. When the foil extends beyond the required margin, colour is used to cover it; then the gold covered portions are outlined in black. Once the paint is dry and the finishing touches are complete, it is glazed. The painting now looks resplendent because of the use of gold and the richness of the colours.

The Thanjavur artist does not regard a portrait as a study of character - the individuality of the subject is identified to a lesser extent than the general decorative effect. In these paintings, the figures are depicted in proportion to their importance; the principal figure therefore is always on a large scale than the rest. Representations of deities under ornate canopies with finely- executed pillars, draperies folded in gentle scallops, garlands of ropes, chandeliers, cushions and furniture, all lend an aura of opulence. The dark - hued Lord Krishna is sometimes depicted as a fair cherub, indicating European influence.

Thanjavur paintings date from the middle of the 18th to the middle of the 19th century. They were painted on wood, glass, mica, ivory and on walls. With the advent of British rule, Englishmen at the kings' court and musicians playing different instruments were painted along with the main subject. Because the painters were Vaishnavites, the subjects were usually Rama, Krishna, Lakshmi, Narasimha, and so on. But the Shaivites introduced Uma Maheshwara, Ganesha, Nataraja, Murugan, Meenakshi, Parvati and other Shaivite deities. This style of painting slowly disappeared because of the time involved and the prohibitive cost. But in recent times, there is a definite revival and Thanjavur paintings are once again becoming very popular. Even today, there are a few families belonging to the original Raja clan living in Thanjavur, Srirangam and Kumbakonam who carry on this traditional art.

Apart from the gem and gold - leaf encrusted paintings of Thanjavur there is a separate though undoubtedly related - tradition of painting on glass, mica and ivory which was introduced around 18th century. The glass paintings, in particular, constituted a difficult genre, as the sequence of steps had to be reversed to achieve the desired result. Thus, after the picture was drawn, it was shaded in first and then decorated with gold leaf a process that resulted in a flat, single-dimensional effect, with doll-like figures. But the painting has the vital quality of folk art, which is its major redeeming feature. There is a remarkable directness of expression, and the message and symbolism are unerring.

It is believed that a group of Chinese artists lived and worked for many of the rulers and merchants whom they painted, and glass paintings are believed to have been introduced into India as a result of Chinese influence. The themes of glass paintings were religious or depictions of women or portraits of patrons. The religious paintings are highly decorative and flat, and the paintings of women heavily stylized. It is in the execution of portraits that an effort was made to infuse reality, to compliment the subjects of the artist's work. There is a dignity and even gentleness in treating these subjects. The British influence is evident in the Victorian architecture of the background, the furniture and even oval format. The fact that religious themes were ideal for the pooja made them instantly popular, and most of the traditional homes in Tamil Nadu still contain glass paintings which are an integral part of the family prayer room.

Conclusion

Tanjore Painting style is one of the oldest South Indian art forms that still exist. These paintings were made with humility, ritual purity and devotion. Mostly, the subjects of these paintings are associated with Hindu Gods and Goddesses. The art form has stood against the test of times through history and went through several innovations. The reason it survived through centuries is the adaptability of the painting style to change the format. Even today, Tanjore Paintings still have a broad appeal. The artists have kept the traditional practices and techniques alive.

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